

Stream-Fed Rings in Massive High- z Galaxies

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1. Cosmic-Web Streams form Rotating Rings/Disks

Galaxies fed by cosmic-web filaments

AMR RAMSES
Teyssier, Dekel

box 300 kpc
res 30 pc z
= 5.0 to 2.5

Streams form Disks at Very High z

$M_{\text{vir}} > 10^{11.3} M_{\odot}$

Streams Feeding a Hi-z Galaxy

Tweed, Dekel, Teyssier
RAMSES Res. 50 pc

100 k

Mass & Angular Momentum

100 kpc

Teyssier, Agertz+ 09

AM Buildup by Cold Streams in 4 Phases

Danovich, Dekel, Hahn+ 15
cosmological simulations

III. inner halo - extended tilted ring
non-linear torques, dissipation
AM loss $\lambda_{\text{cold}} \rightarrow 0.04$ & alignment

II. outer halo
AM transport, $j \sim \text{const.}$
 $\lambda_{\text{cold}} \sim 3\lambda_{\text{dm}} \sim 0.1$ DM mix

I. cosmic web
linear tidal torques
 \rightarrow impact parameter
 $\lambda_{\text{cold}} \sim 1.7\lambda_{\text{dm}}$

IV. inner disc (+ bulge)
disk instability, outflows
 $\lambda_{\text{baryons}} \sim 0.03$

spin parameter $\lambda \sim \frac{J/M}{\sqrt{2}R_v V_v}$

III. An Extended Tilted Ring about the Disk

gas density

Danovich+ 12,15

Stewart+ 11-15, Pichon+ 11-15

Observable in Ly α : 30% of l.o.s with DLAS column density

30 kpc

stream lines

expressway entrance

Violent Disk Instability (VDI) at High z

Ceverino+ ART-AMR cosmological simulations at 25pc resolution

A typical massive SFG at $z \sim 2$: gas-rich, highly perturbed, clumpy rotating disk/ring: $H/R \sim \sigma/V \sim f_{\text{cold}} \sim 0.2$

A typical star-forming galaxy at $z \sim 2$:
clumpy, rotating, extended disk/ring & a bulge

H α star-forming
regions

color-code
velocity field

Genzel et al 08

Clump Migration in a Few Orbits

Ceverino, Dekel, Bournaud 10

VDI: Mass Inflow & Clump Migration

In a violently unstable disk (VDI):
torques induce transport of angular momentum out
→ rapid mass inflow, clump migration

$$t_{\text{inflow}} \approx 2\delta_d^{-2} t_{\text{orb}}$$

$$\delta_d \equiv (M_d / M_{\text{tot}})$$

cold mass fraction

Dekel, Sari,
Ceverino 09

$\delta_d \ll 1 \rightarrow$ disk evacuation in a few orbital times

2. Wet Compaction to Blue Nuggets Supports Extended Ring in Massive Galaxies

Dekel & Burkert 14, Zolotov+15, Tacchella+16a,b, Dekel, Lapiner+19

Dekel+ 19

Compaction -> Blue Nugget -> Central Quenching

Compaction and Quenching in Simulations

Zolotov+15
Tacchella+16
Dekel+17

Observed L-Shape Track

Barro+17

Wet Compaction to a Blue Nugget and Disk/Ring Formation

VELA-3 cosmological simulations 25pc res (Ceverino, Dekel, Primack)

Robust Post-Compaction Rings

Why is ring long-lived?

Compaction -> Extended Ring

In VDI: torques induce AM transport out -> rapid mass inflow

$$t_{\text{inflow}} \approx \delta_d^{-2} t_{\text{orb}}$$

$$\delta_d \equiv (M_d / M_{\text{tot}}) \quad \text{cold mass fraction}$$

Dekel, Sari,
Ceverino 09

Gravitational Torques by Spiral Structure on Outer Ring

tightly wound, thin disk

Dekel+19

pitch angle: $\tan^2 \alpha \approx 4\delta_d^2 \ll 1$

$$(\Delta L / L)_{\text{orbit}} \approx 3A_m^2 \delta_d \tan^2 \alpha \approx \delta_d^3$$

Post-compaction rings don't shrink

$$t_{\text{inflow}} \approx \delta_d^{-3} t_{\text{orb}}$$

- In-streams with high AM
- Massive bulge -> $\delta_d \ll 1$ -> $\alpha \ll 1$ ring

$$t_{\text{inflow}} \gg 10 t_{\text{orbit}}$$

Why gas ring survives?

timescales:

$$t_{\text{orb}} \sim 1 \text{ Gyr } (1+z)^{-3/2}$$

$$t_{\text{acc}} \sim 30 \text{ Gyr } (1+z)^{-5/2} \sim 30 t_{\text{orb}} (1+z)^{-1}$$

$$t_{\text{inflow}} \sim \delta_d^{-3} t_{\text{orb}} > 30 t_{\text{orb}}$$

$$t_{\text{SFR}} \sim \varepsilon^{-1} t_{\text{ff}} \sim 4 t_{\text{orb}}$$

$\rightarrow t_{\text{acc}} < t_{\text{inflow}} \rightarrow$ ring accumulates

$\rightarrow t_{\text{SFR}} \ll t_{\text{inflow}} \rightarrow$ dissipative inflow is impossible

Blue Nuggets at $\sim M_{\text{crit}}$ in Simulations & CANDELS

$$M_{\text{star}} \sim 10^{10} M_{\odot}$$

$$M_{\text{vir}} \sim 10^{11.5} M_{\odot}$$

Zolotov+15, Tomassetti+16

A Mass Threshold for Disks/Rings

VELA-3 cosmological simulations 25pc res (Ceverino, Dekel, Primack)

Omri
Ginzburg

Disks/rings in $M_{\text{vir}} > 2 \times 10^{11} M_{\odot}$

$M_{\text{star}} > 10^9 M_{\odot}$

all redshifts

Compaction-Driven Disk/Ring Formation

Diskiness

Expansion factor (time) with respect to the major compaction event

Rings+Bulges in CANDELS

Zhiyuan, Giavalisco, ...

2.6'x2.6' subfield of medium-deep GOODS-S

$M_* > 10^{9.5} M_\odot$ $z = 0.5-2$

U

B

H

Rings+Bulges in CANDELS

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U

B

H

~ half the galaxies !

Observed H α Rings & Massive Bulge

$z \sim 2$ Genzel+14

Extended Star Forming Ring & a Massive Bulge

$z=0$ Salim+ 2012 Most galaxies in Green Valley

Clumpy Ring?

The ring is Toomre unstable

$$Q \approx (\sigma/V) \delta_d^{-1} \approx 1$$

Dekel, Sari, Ceverino 09

$$t_{\text{inflow}}/t_{\text{orb}} \approx \delta_d^{-3} \gg 1$$

Ring with No Bulge?

$$t_{\text{inflow}} \approx \delta_d^{-3} t_{\text{orb}}$$

δ_d may be low due to central dark matter

Genzel+17,19: at $z \sim 2$ frequent rings

either about a massive bulge with low DM fraction
or about a massive central DM

3. Disruption of Low-Mass Rings/Disks by Merger-Driven Spin Flips

A Mass Threshold for Disks/Rings

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Omri
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Disks/rings in $M_{\text{vir}} > 2 \times 10^{11} M_{\odot}$

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all redshifts

Spin Flips

$\Delta t \sim 100-200$ Myr

Spin Flips in an Orbital Time

Neistein, Dekel 08

$$t_{\text{flip}} \approx \frac{M_{\text{bar}}}{\dot{M}_{\text{bar}}} = \frac{M_{\text{star}}}{M_{\text{vir}}} \frac{M_{\text{bar}}}{M_{\text{star}}} \frac{M_{\text{vir}}}{f_b \dot{M}_{\text{vir}}} \rightarrow t_{\text{flip}} \propto M_{\text{vir}} (1+z)^{-3/2}$$

$$\frac{M_{\text{star}}}{M_{\text{vir}}} \propto M_{\text{vir}}$$

Behroozi+13,18
Dekel, Woo 03

$$\frac{M_{\text{bar}}}{M_{\text{star}}} \propto (1+z)$$

Tacconi+18

$$\frac{M_{\text{vir}}}{\dot{M}_{\text{vir}}} \propto (1+z)^{-5/2}$$

Dekel+13

$$t_{\text{orb}} \propto (1+z)^{-3/2}$$

$$\frac{t_{\text{flip}}}{t_{\text{orb}}} = \frac{M_{\text{vir}}}{M_{\text{crit}}}$$

$$M_{\text{crit}} \approx 10^{11} M_{\odot}$$

Disk disruption below a critical mass

Spin Flips in a Disk Orbital Time

Spin flips in node mergers,
where stream pattern changes

AMR RAMSES
Teyssier, Dekel

box 300 kpc
res 30 pc z
= 5.0 to 2.5

Conclusions

Cosmic-web streams form extended gas rings/disks

Violently unstable \rightarrow giant clumps

Rings/disk disrupt on an orbital time by merger-driven spin flips at $M_{\text{vir}} < 10^{11.3} M_{\odot}$ and survive above it, at all z

Wet-compaction events, at $M_{\text{vir}} \sim 10^{11.5} M_{\odot}$, are followed by long-lived rings

Rings are stabilized against shrinkage by a central mass, a post-compaction massive bulge or central dark matter

Obs. challenge: explore rings about bulges at high z